

Rapid Response Brief

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What can research evidence tell us about: Interventions to Improve HPV Screening Rates in Mukono District

Key messages

Research indicates that successful strategies to improve HPV screening rates focus on imparting knowledge, encouraging women to undergo screening, and making the sampling process more convenient. Tailoring interventions to local contexts and combining multiple strategies can enhance their effectiveness. The interventions include;

- ➔ **Invitation and Reminder Systems:** Sending reminder messages, particularly through phone calls and SMS, has been shown to significantly increase screening rates. Personalized invitations from medical professionals can further enhance participation.
- ➔ **Education:** Caution needs to be exercised in using print material as the women need to be able and willing to read. Video education materials and face-to-face home visits have better impact.
- ➔ **Counselling:** Face-to-face and telephone counselling by trained healthcare workers significantly increase screening rates.
- ➔ **Self-Sampling:** Mukono District is also implementing this strategy, therefore modifications to it would be the addition of other strategies to further harness its impact.
- ➔ **Combined Interventions:** Combining interventions, such as self-sampling strategy, personalized invitations, informative leaflets, and reminder phone calls have the potential for the highest impact.

Where did this Rapid Response come from?

This document was created in response to a specific question from a policy maker in Uganda.

It was prepared by the Center for Rapid Evidence Synthesis (ACRES), at the Uganda country node of the Regional East African Community Health (REACH) Policy Initiative

+ Included:

- **Key findings** from research
- **Considerations about the relevance** of this research for policy decisions in Uganda

✗ Not included:

- Recommendations
- Detailed descriptions

Short summary

Background:

The Uganda Ministry of Health monitors HPV screening through district-level data collection, incentivizing active monitoring. In Mukono District, efforts have focused on educating HIV-infected women and providing sample self-collection kits for convenience. Despite these efforts, HPV screening uptake remains low at 44%. This issue is widespread in Uganda. To improve screening rates, the Mukono District Health Team is seeking evidence on interventions used to improve HPV screening rates to develop a tailored solution.

Rapid Response question: *How can HPV screening rates be increased among women attending HIV clinics in Mukono District?*

Findings:

Strategies to improve HPV screening rates focus on imparting knowledge, encouraging women to undergo screening, and making the sampling process more convenient. These interventions include;

- **Invitation and Reminders:** Studies that assessed invitation and reminder letters showed increase in screening uptake compared to no reminders. For Mukono district, letters can be replaced by phone calls, use of SMS messages and possible social media where women own smart phones. Other forms of reminders include phone call reminders made by any one in the healthcare system or made by a physician.
- **Self-Sampling:** HPV self-sampling showed higher increases in screening uptake. Since this is an intervention that Mukono District is also implementing, the modifications to it would be the addition of other strategies to further harness the impact of the intervention.
- **Education:** Education through printed materials, videos, and face-to-face interactions significantly improved screening rates. Face-to-face education in homes was found to be particularly effective, increasing screening by six times compared to no education.
- **Counselling:** Face-to-face and telephone counselling by trained healthcare workers significantly increased screening rates by 23% compared to no intervention.
- **Media Campaigns:** Media campaigns through culturally sensitive radio and television ads had limited impact on screening uptake. The feasibility of this intervention is challenged by the lack of regional media outlets in Uganda, with any intervention in this category being mostly nationwide.
- **Combined Interventions:** Combining interventions, such as personalized invitation letters, informative leaflets, and reminder phone calls, showed varied effectiveness. Personalized invitation letters with leaflets and phone calls increased screening coverage by 27.8% compared to 9% for no intervention.

Conclusion:

Strategies to improve HPV screening rates focus on imparting knowledge, encouraging women to undergo screening, and making the sampling process more convenient. Designing effective interventions should center around these principles. Combining multiple interventions is a feasible alternative as it can result in a higher impact as compared to single interventions.

Background

The Uganda Ministry of Health actively monitors Human Papillomavirus (HPV) screening through data collected at districts across the country. This has incentivized the districts to actively monitor their coverage of HPV screening. In Mukono District, the District Health Team focused efforts of HPV screening towards the HIV infected women, who are one of the most vulnerable populations to cervical cancer infections. The interventions the district opted for are focused education of women about the importance of HPV screening and the use of sample self-collection kits for women attending HIV clinics. The option of sample self-collection kits allows women to collect samples at their convenience and return them during their subsequent clinic visits, an approach intended to address the discomfort and uneasiness associated with sample collection by healthcare providers.

However, despite this, the uptake of HPV screening services in Mukono District remains low, with only an estimated 44% of women attending HIV clinics participating in the screening. This challenge is not unique to Mukono District but is prevalent across the country. To address this issue, the Mukono District Health Team is exploring the design of an intervention to improve HPV screening rates among the target population. The Assistant District Health Officer has reached out to ACRES, requesting evidence on various researched and implemented interventions to inform the development of a tailored solution for Mukono District.

Rapid Response question: *How can HPV screening rates be increased among women attending HIV clinics in Mukono District?*

Summary of findings

Screening for Human Papillomavirus (HPV) is a crucial intervention in the fight against cervical cancer. Despite its importance, many countries have struggled to increase the coverage of HPV screening, prompting the development of various interventions aimed at addressing this challenge. This rapid response brief provides evidence on different intervention options and their impacts on improving HPV screening rates, as assessed through randomized controlled trials (RCTs).

While the specific question pertains to HPV screening among HIV-positive women attending HIV clinics in Mukono District, the evidence presented here applies to the broader population. These intervention options are relevant to the target population in Mukono District, as there are no specific characteristics that would render these interventions inapplicable.

How this Rapid Response was prepared

After clarifying the question being asked, we searched for systematic reviews, local or national evidence from Uganda, and other relevant research.

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INTERVENTIONS IMPLEMENTED TO IMPROVE HPV SCREENING RATES AMONG WOMEN:

All interventions designed at increasing HPV screening uptake aim at achieving behavioral change of women through either imparting knowledge about the importance of the screening or reminding them about the importance of screening or making the process as convenient as possible for the women.

The assessed interventions include;

1. Invitation letters
2. Reminder letters
3. Phone reminders
4. Physician reminders
5. HPV self-sampling
6. Education
7. Counselling
8. Media campaigns
9. A combination of any number of the above interventions

The details of these options are presented below;

Study	Interventions	Study Design	Outcome	Contextualization and discussion
(1, 2)	Modified vs. standard invitation letter	RCT	The modified invitation letter had an information brochure in addition to the standard invitation. The standard invitation had information on purpose of the pap smear, whom it is for and the screening is done. The intervention group had 2% less women going for screening compared to the control group. However, the difference was not significant. Therefore, there was no difference between the two interventions in terms of improving uptake of HPV screening.	This study was not among HIV positive population; however, the findings are valid for HIV positive population. For the context of Mukono district, the invitation letter can be replaced by information sent through a phone SMS message . The additional information given in form of a brochure would be most feasible through the use of a smart phone, otherwise, the message can as well be sent by SMS.
(1, 2)	Reminder letter vs. no reminder letter	RCT	Study by Eaker et al., reported 7.9% more women attending screening in the group that received a reminder letter as compared to that without the letter, the difference being statistically significant. Therefore, sending reminder letters resulted in a meaningful difference (more uptake of	This was not among HIV positive population, however, the findings are valid for HIV positive population. As letters are not a feasible alternative in Mukono district, the use of reminder

			screening) as compared to the group that did not receive a reminder letter.	phone SMS' would be a practical alternative to the letters.
(1, 3, 4)		RCT	Morrell et al., reported results by age group. For women aged 20-24, reported a pap test ratio in those who received reminder letters of 4.02% compared to 4.09% of those who did not receive reminder letter. For age group 25-29, it was 3.83% Vs 2.58% and age group 30-34, it was 3,6% Vs 2.58%.	The use of reminders was found to be effective in improving uptake of HPV screening, except for the age group 20-24 years where the reminder letters were found to have no effect on uptake of the intervention.
		RCT	McDowell et al., found that among women who received reminder letters, 25.9% were screened for HPV as compared to 13.7% who did not receive reminder letters.	
		Systematic review	A total of 9 studies included in this category. All but one study favoured invitations over no invitations. The one study that favoured no invitation did not have a significant difference between the two groups. Invitations from a doctor received better responses as compared to the screening program coordinator and nurses.	Where possible, the invitation should come from a medical doctor as this was shown to give better response as compared to invitations from other health workers.
(1, 2, 4)	Phone reminder vs. no phone reminder	RCT	Eaker et al.'s study showed that compared to the group that did not receive a phone reminder , the group that received a phone reminder had 21.7% more women attending for HPV screening.	These two studies demonstrate that phone reminders from a healthcare worker to the target women are effective in improving uptake of HPV screening.
(1, 5)		RCT	A study by McDowell et al., found 20.0% of the women who received a phone reminder went for HPV screening as compared to 13.7% of the women who did not receive phone reminders. Similar results were reported by Binstock et al(4).	The phone reminder intervention is feasible in Mukono district as the mobile phone penetration has significantly increased over the last 5 years with a good number of the adult population owning a handset.
(1, 5)	Physician reminder vs. no reminder	RCT	A study by McDowell et al., found 16.1% of the women who received reminders from physicians received HPV screening as compared to 13.7% of the group that did not receive physician reminders.	The number of physicians in the health system staffing structures limited, which pauses a challenge to this intervention. However, working with nurses and mid-

				wives at the facilities, these can be capable replacements for the physicians and therefore a feasible alternative.
(1, 6, 7)	HPV self-sampling vs. reminder letter	RCT	<p>Virtanen et al., found that 26.6% of the women in the self-sampling group were screened as compared to 21.5% in the reminder letter group with a 95% CI of 1.01 to 1.48.</p> <p>A study by Racey et al., showed that women in the self-sampling group were 3.7 times more likely to go for HPV screening as compared to women in the standard of care group.</p>	Both interventions resulted in high increases in uptake of HPV screening, however, self-sampling had higher increases, with the difference between the two interventions being significant. Both interventions can be implemented in Mukono district. However, as Mukono district has already implemented self-sampling, it is important to explore other strategies, in addition to the self-sampling to increase the uptake of HPV screening.
(4, 8)	Education	Systematic review	<p>The use of printed materials for education versus no intervention resulted in more people in the printed material group going for screening as compared to those in the control group. However, this effect was not statistically significant.</p> <p>When compared to no intervention, the use of videos for patient education resulted in a fourfold increase in uptake of HPV screening.</p> <p>Studies that compared face-to-face education in the homes of the target population also reported higher numbers of women going for HPV screening as compared to those who were not visited for education on HPV screening. HPV screening was reported to be 6 times higher in the homes that received education as compared to those that did not.</p>	Patient education is a feasible intervention in Mukono district. Material can be developed for print and video means of education. Face-to-face education in homes can also be designed by use of the Village Health Team. However, the use of printed material should be used with caution, as it requires the women to be able and willing to read the provided material. In addition, the studies showed that use of printed materials had less impact as compared to other education strategies.
(4, 9, 10)	Counselling	Systematic review	<p>A study by Ward et al., assessed a face-to-face counselling intervention by a doctor versus no intervention. Another study by Rimer et al., assessed telephone counselling and</p>	For patient counselling to have the impact demonstrated in the two studies, the health care worker delivering the

			patient prompts , versus patient prompts alone (control group) and provider prompts alone. Both studies demonstrated a higher impact on uptake of HPV screening among the counselling group as compared to control group. The counselling group had 23% higher numbers of women going for HPV screening compared to the control group with a confidence interval of 1.07 to 1.41.	counselling must be adequately trained in counselling and equipped with enough information on HPV screening cervical cancer.
(8)	Media campaign	Systematic review	Culturally sensitive media education campaigns were found to have limited impact on uptake of screening in two studies.	Media campaigns through the use of radio and television ads are feasible. However, Uganda lacks regional television and radio stations, therefore, the intervention would be more wide spread than Mukono, which would result in higher costs. However, it should be noted that the intervention showed limited impact.
(7, 11)	Combined interventions	RCT	The study assessed four interventions i.e. personalized invitation letter (I1) Vs a personalized invitation letter plus and informative leaflet (I2) Vs personalized invitation letter plus the informative leaflet and a personalized phone call three days before the appointment (I3) Vs no intervention (I4). I1 resulted into 27.8% increase in HPV screening coverage as compared to 26.2%, 37.3%, and 9% for I2, I3 and I4 respectively.	The combination of interventions is feasible for the district.

Other considerations in designing an effective intervention include; the **involvement of lay health workers in women screening** in addition to a female nurse practitioner resulted in increased uptake of the HPV screening. Additional considerations include the **involvement of health promotion nurses** in sensitizing women on HPV screening, and the **use of female smear takers** as these resulted in increased uptake compared to procedures that did not use health promotion nurses and male smear takers(4). Whereas some studies assessed the impact of single interventions and other assessed the effect of combined interventions, it is crucial to note that employing a **combination of interventions is likely produce a higher impact than single interventions** (8, 11).

Conclusions

Several interventions have been studied to improve HPV screening rates, focusing on imparting knowledge, encouraging women to undergo screening, and making the sampling process more convenient. Designing effective interventions should center around these principles. Combining multiple interventions can leverage the strengths of each, addressing the gaps left by single strategies. Tailoring approaches to local feasibility is crucial, as increasing HPV screening rates remains a critical goal.

References

1. Albrow R, Blomberg K, Kitchener H, Brabin L, Patnick J, Tishelman C, et al. Interventions to improve cervical cancer screening uptake amongst young women: a systematic review. *Acta Oncol.* 2014;53(4):445-51.
2. Eaker S, Adami HO, Granath F, Wilander E, Sparén P. A large population-based randomized controlled trial to increase attendance at screening for cervical cancer. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2004;13(3):346-54.
3. Morrell S, Taylor R, Zeckendorf S, Niciak A, Wain G, Ross J. How much does a reminder letter increase cervical screening among under-screened women in NSW? *Aust N Z J Public Health.* 2005;29(1):78-84.
4. Forbes C, Jepson R, Martin-Hirsch P. Interventions targeted at women to encourage the uptake of cervical screening. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2002(3):Cd002834.
5. McDowell I, Newell C, Rosser W. Computerized reminders to encourage cervical screening in family practice. *J Fam Pract.* 1989;28(4):420-4.
6. Virtanen A, Nieminen P, Luostarinen T, Anttila A. Self-sample HPV tests as an intervention for nonattendees of cervical cancer screening in Finland: a randomized trial. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2011;20(9):1960-9.
7. Racey CS, Gesink DC, Burchell AN, Trivers S, Wong T, Rebbapragada A. Randomized Intervention of Self-Collected Sampling for Human Papillomavirus Testing in Under-Screened Rural Women: Uptake of Screening and Acceptability. *J Womens Health (Larchmt).* 2016;25(5):489-97.
8. Lu M, Moritz S, Lorenzetti D, Sykes L, Straus S, Quan H. A systematic review of interventions to increase breast and cervical cancer screening uptake among Asian women. *BMC Public Health.* 2012;12:413.
9. Rimer BK, Conaway M, Lyna P, Glassman B, Yarnall KS, Lipkus I, et al. The impact of tailored interventions on a community health center population. *Patient Educ Couns.* 1999;37(2):125-40.
10. Ward JE, Boyle K, Redman S, Sanson-Fisher RW. Increasing women's compliance with opportunistic cervical cancer screening: a randomized trial. *Am J Prev Med.* 1991;7(5):285-91.
11. Acera A, Manresa JM, Rodriguez D, Rodriguez A, Bonet JM, Trapero-Bertran M, et al. Increasing Cervical Cancer Screening Coverage: A Randomised, Community-Based Clinical Trial. *PLoS One.* 2017;12(1):e0170371.

What is Rapid Response?

Rapid Responses address the needs of policymakers and managers for research evidence that has been appraised and contextualised in a matter of hours or days, if it is going to be of value to them. The Responses address questions about arrangements for organising, financing and governing systems, and strategies for implementing changes.

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ACRES' collaborators:

Regional East African Community
Health Policy Initiative

**Regional East African
Community Health Policy
Initiative**

EVIPnet

This summary was prepared by

Kayongo Edward, Shery Ritah Ahirirwe, Perez Kirya, Peter Kasadah, Caroline Nakalema, Pastan Lusiba, and Ismael Kawooya, The Center for Rapid Evidence Synthesis (CRES), Plot 24 Wampewo Close, Kololo, Kampala, P.O Box 110226, Kampala, Uganda

Conflicts of interest

None known.

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For more information contact

Name: Kayongo Edward

Email address: ekayongo@acres.or.ug